

Impact Damage Tolerance of Composites Reinforced with Kevlar® Aramid Fibers

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ABSTRACT

Impact damage tolerance of monolithic panels of epoxy reinforced with KEVLAR® 49 and KEVLAR 29 aramid fibers, E-glass, and "THORNEL" 300 graphite have been studied via instrumented drop weight testing. Impact energy to the point of catastrophic failure (through-cracking) is related by a semi-empirical model to fiber properties, namely the strain energy to failure in tension of fiber/resin composite strands. On this basis, the reinforcing fibers can be ordered in terms of energy absorbed in impact per unit composite weight from greatest to least: KEVLAR 29, E-glass, KEVLAR 49, and THORNEL 300. Hybrids of KEVLAR 49/graphite which demonstrate an advantage over all-graphite reinforcement in total impact energy have also been tested.

TEXT

Impact damage tolerance of advanced composite materials is an area of considerable concern to the composites community. We will review some recent work at Du Pont which we believe contributes to a better understanding of impact damage in composites, making three points:

- Reinforcement of KEVLAR aramid fibers can significantly improve the impact damage tolerance of composites if used in place of or in conjunction with graphite fiber.
- Instrumented impact testing is a powerful tool for understanding impact.
- The relative impact damage tolerance of composites in certain situations can be predicted from fiber properties.

INSTRUMENTED IMPACT TESTING

There is much confusion in the composites community over impact, largely, I believe, because there is no single criterion for judging damage tolerance. Different applications dictate the use of different criteria. Broad generalizations

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about the performance of a particular reinforcement based on its performance versus a particular, limited failure criterion, can be very misleading. For example, measurements of the energy required to completely penetrate a panel may rank two reinforcements differently than measurements of retained compression strength after low energy impact. And either result is significant only if it is relevant to the application. The instrumented impact test, while it does not remove the need for different criteria, at least clarifies what is being measured and helps to define consistent failure criteria. It does this by recording the actual load and energy history during the course of the impact event (Figure 1). (1) The various features of the load-time trace can be related to observations on the impacted panels, as has been done in the figure. In the example above, energy to complete penetration corresponds most closely to the quantity E_t . Retained strength after low energy impact depends on the relation between the energy of the impacting object, E_0 , and E_i , the energy at which the first fiber damage occurs. If E_0 is less than E_i , strength loss will probably be minimal, while if E_0 is above E_i , it may be significant. Of course, the actual strength loss depends on how the energy is dissipated in the composite.

Each of the primary points on this curve is potentially important, depending on the application. Since the first aircraft applications of KEVLAR are primarily in non-structural or semi-structural parts where the in-use failure criteria are:

- visible front face damage or
- existence of a path (through-crack) for moisture penetration,

we choose the point corresponding to the first through crack, P_m , and the associated energy E_m , as the basis for comparison of materials. Energy absorbed is the most important parameter: the key to surviving impact is absorbing all the energy of the impacting object without damage. The load trace serves only to define the proper point to take the energy.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The materials selected for our work are shown in Figure 2. These are fabrics preimpregnated with a 250°F-cure epoxy resin qualified for exterior non-structural and semi-structural parts on the new generation of Boeing aircraft. Since many of these parts are to be hybrids of KEVLAR 49 aramid and graphite as thin face sheets on NOMEX® aramid honeycomb core, we have tested some panels of this type, and more work in these is planned. However, the primary results to date are on monolithic panels ranging from 40 to 250 mil thickness, reinforced with either fabric of all-KEVLAR or all-graphite. These panels allow us to study the performance of the two fibers without the complication introduced by honeycomb core.

The test conditions are shown in Figure 3. The energy of the falling weight was sufficient to completely penetrate the panel. In a few cases the indenter was stopped prior to complete penetration to examine the nature of the damage, and it is on this basis that the interpretation of Figure 1 is made. Typical traces for reinforcement of KEVLAR and graphite are shown in Figure 4. The panels with KEVLAR experience a softer failure mode. Damage initiates with a small load drop at P_i , but load continues to increase until P_m when through cracking occurs. Graphite fails more brittly. When failure initiates at P_i , through-crack propagation occurs without significantly more energy absorption and $P_i = P_m$.

Energy, E_m , is plotted versus panel weight in Figure 5. Panels reinforced with KEVLAR 49 have about twice the energy absorbing capacity of graphite to the point of through cracking. KEVLAR 29 absorbs about 25% more energy than KEVLAR 49. As we have seen earlier, the tensile properties of KEVLAR 29 are similar to those of S-2 glass. As a reinforcement fiber KEVLAR 29 offers both good damage tolerance and useful mechanical properties.

Three different fabrics of KEVLAR 49 and two of KEVLAR 29 were tested representing different weave geometries, yarn diameters, and per ply thicknesses. These appear to be indistinguishable within each fiber type in this test, although there is evidence that fabric-related differences do exist in honeycomb core laminates.

Ultrasonic C-scans of failed panels were made to assess delamination (Figures 6A and 6B). Delamination is about the same for KEVLAR 49 aramid and graphite - in all cases it is localized to the area around the point of impact. It has been suggested that excessive delamination resulting from poor fiber-resin adhesion is responsible for the impact advantage of reinforcement of KEVLAR, but clearly this is not the case. In fact, as we shall see, the primary contribution to impact energy, at least up to the point of through cracking, is tensile strain energy of the fibers.

TENSILE ENERGY ANALYSIS

Tensile properties of the fabrics were determined from (0, 90) lay-ups of the fabric prepreps and used to calculate the quantity t^2/E , which is proportional to the tensile strain energy (toughness or area under the stress-strain curve). The impact data are plotted versus this parameter in Figure 7 showing a reasonably good proportionality for panels less than about 200 mil thickness. This result strongly suggests that impact up to the point of through cracking in these panels is dominated by the tensile properties of the fibers, and not by delamination, compressive yielding, or other potential energy absorbing mechanisms. Membrane stresses, which become significant when panel deflection exceeds 2-3 times its thickness, are probably dominant in the failure process. When panel thickness exceeds 200 mils, the proportionality appears to break down, as expected since flexural stresses become more important in thick panels. Figure 8 shows specific impact energy, E_m , normalized to panel weight, plotted vs. specific tensile strain energy derived from published resin impregnated strand data for the different fibers. A reasonable correlation exists and the strand data predict the ordering of reinforcement from best to worst:

KEVLAR 29 aramid
KEVLAR 49 aramid
Thornel 300 graphite

as found experimentally. Our conclusion is that in a common resin system, in panels less than about 200 mils, the effectiveness of various reinforcement fibers in impact damage tolerance, as measured by the energy to form a through crack, can be predicted from the fiber tensile properties. It may also be possible to admit resin as a variable if its effect on tensile properties is included. However, this has to be confirmed experimentally.

HONEYCOMB CORE

Our results on honeycomb core are not yet complete. However, from the existing data it is apparent that the situation is more complex than in monolithic panels. First of all, in very thin face sheets, there is a significant amount of "fine structure" in the load traces which changes as the number of plies in the face sheet increases (Figure 9). In addition, effects which were found to be insignificant in monolithic panels, such as ply orientation, appear to be significant in thin faces. For example, 45°ply against the core is somewhat better than a 0° ply.

Because of the complexity of the curves and the limited amount of data, it has not been possible to pick a single consistent point defining through cracking of the face sheet as in the case of monolithic panels. Therefore, we plot the equivalent of E_t , in this case the energy to completely penetrate the front face sheet, vs. face sheet weight in Figure 10. The energy absorbed by

reinforcement of KEVLAR 49 aramid (we have as yet no KEVLAR 29 aramid data) is greater than that for graphite, but the differences are not as great as we saw in the monolithic panels. In addition, the hybrid panels, which have been added in Figure 11, also show some advantages.

In the honeycomb core panels, it appears that fabric construction does have an effect on impact damage tolerance: the two fabrics of 10 mil per ply thickness, S-285 and S-281, are better than the 4.5 mil per ply S-120, and of these the plain weave S-281 is better than the satin weave S-285. This is consistent with previous Du Pont data.(2)

A comparison of load traces for a baseline graphite face sheet, two plies of fabric, a two-ply hybrid, and one- and two-ply face sheets of all-KEVLAR 49 is shown in Figure 12. The hybrid gives higher load and higher energy absorption throughout the event, and the two-ply KEVLAR is higher yet. Interestingly, the single ply face sheet of KEVLAR 49 gives impact as good as two plies of graphite, offering the possibility of saving in both weight and assembly time without loss of impact damage tolerance. A single ply of KEVLAR 29 is expected to be even more attractive for applications where the lower modulus can be tolerated.

SUMMARY

We have reported data from an on-going experimental program at Du Pont on the impact damage tolerance of composites, and particularly those reinforced with KEVLAR aramid fibers in woven fabrics. The results demonstrate the power of the instrumented impact test as an aid to understanding the impact event. The experimental data show that reinforcement of KEVLAR, and particularly KEVLAR 29, can give significantly greater impact damage tolerance than graphite, and that hybrids in thin face sheets also offer an advantage over all-graphite. Finally, the analysis shows that impact of monolithic panels up to the point of through cracking is dominated by the tensile properties of the fibers, not by delamination or compressive yielding, and that the relative damage tolerance of reinforcement fibers in a given matrix is predictable from fiber properties.

REFERENCES

- (1) Ireland, D. R., "Procedures and Problems Associated with Reliable Control of the Instrumented Impact Test", ASTM STP 563, 1973, p. 3.
- (2) Miner, L. H., Wolffe, R. A., and Zweben, C. H., "Fatigue, Creep, and Impact Resistance of Aramid Fiber Reinforced Composites", ASTM STP 580, 1975, p. 549.

INSTRUMENTED IMPACT TESTING

MAJOR POINTS OF INTEREST

- P_i, E_i LOAD, ENERGY
INCIPIENT DAMAGE POINT
(BACK FACE CRACKING)
- P_m, E_m LOAD, ENERGY AT MAXIMUM
OR FAILURE POINT
(THROUGH CRACK)
- E_t TOTAL ENERGY
(FULL PENETRATION)
- E_p $E_t - E_m$, PROPAGATION ENERGY

Figure 1

FIBER	FABRIC STYLE	PREIMPREGNATED FABRICS		YARN DENIER*	WEAVE	PER PLY THICKNESS mil
		FIBER WEIGHT oz/yd ²	FIBER VOLUME %			
Kevlar® 29 Aramid	S-710	2.0	48.0	200	Plain	4.0
	S-728	6.5	47.1	1500	Plain	12.8
Kevlar® 49 Aramid	S-283	5.0	42.2	1140	CrowFoot Satin	10
	S-285	4.0	44.8	1140	Plain	10
	S-110	1.8	41.7	195	Plain	3.8
Thornel 300 Graphite	3K-70-PW	5.7	48.3	~2100	Plain	8.8

All Hexcel F-153 Epoxy
 *Kevlar® Aramid Honeycomb Core, 3pcf, 1/4" thick, 1/8" cell
 * Denier = Weight in grams of 9000m of yarn or fiber.

Figure 2

IMPACT TEST CONDITIONS

EFFECTS TECHNOLOGY, INC., INSTRUMENTED DROP TOWER

Monolithic Panels

Incident Energy, $E_0 = 234$ ft-lb
 Incident Velocity, $V_0 = 8$ fps

Indentor $\frac{1}{2}$ " ϕ Hemisphere

Honeycomb Core Panels

Incident Energy, $E_0 = 13.6$ ft-lb
 Incident Velocity, $V_0 = 3$ fps

Indentor $5/8$ " ϕ Hemisphere

Samples supported on 5×5 in² frame.

Figure 3

TYPICAL LOAD-TIME TRACES IN INSTRUMENTED IMPACT OF KEVLAR® AND GRAPHITE

"KEVLAR" 49

"THORNEL" 300

Figure 4

Figure 5

C-SCANS OF IMPACT DAMAGED PANELS

Figure 6

Figure 7

IMPACT ENERGY PER UNIT WEIGHT OF COMPOSITE PANELS

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure 10

IMPACT ENERGY OF HYBRID FACE SHEETS ON HONEYCOMB CORE

Figure 11

Figure 12